

Microgram Determination of Ascorbic Acid in Pharmaceutical Preparations, Urine, Blood Plasma and Fruit Juices

V. N. PATHAK, A. L. SINGH and I. C. SHUKLA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 5 November 1982, revised 29 July 1983,
accepted 30 May 1984

VARIOUS oxidants have been used for the titrimetric¹⁻¹⁰ and colorimetric¹¹⁻¹³ determination of ascorbic acid. Many of these methods suffer from the drawback of longer reaction time and lesser sensitivity. The standard method^{11,14} used in pathological laboratories involves rigid control of temperature (37°), a reaction time of 3 hours and a complicated procedure. Moreover, the determination of ascorbic acid in urine is done titrimetrically¹⁵ by a separate procedure. The present method utilises a quick reaction, gives better accuracy and more precise results. It is a simple and general procedure for the determination of ascorbic acid in its various forms and in biological fluids.

Experimental

Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter was used for the absorbance measurement. Ammonium meta vanadate (A. R.) solution (0.3 M) 3.5 g (Reanal, Budapest), was made in 10% sulphuric acid (AnalaR, sp. gr., 1.84).

Preparation of samples: A fresh solution of pure ascorbic acid (tablets or injection ampule) was prepared in distilled water to give a concentration 1 mg ml⁻¹. 5 ml blood plasma was added dropwise with shaking to 5 ml trichloroacetic acid (20%) in a 25 ml centrifuge tube and stirred to obtain a fine suspension. The suspension was allowed to stand for 5 min and then centrifuged. The clear supernatant solution was filtered and used for the determination of ascorbic acid.

40 ml urine sample was taken and mixed well with 10 ml metaphosphoric acid (20%). The solution of urine was employed to estimate ascorbic acid.

Fruit juice of tomato, lemon and orange was mixed with 5 ml trichloroacetic acid (20%) to retard the oxidation of ascorbic acid and to precipitate protein etc. The solution was centrifuged and the supernatant layer was treated with 10 ml metaphosphoric acid (3%) and filtered. The filtrate was used for the determination of ascorbic acid.

Procedure: Aliquots containing 40 µg-0.8 mg ml⁻¹ ascorbic acid were prepared by diluting the stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) with distilled water. The test solution (5 ml), standard ascorbic acid

solution (5 ml, 200 µg ml⁻¹), and distilled water (5 ml) were taken in three separate stoppered corning test tubes. To each test tube ammonium meta vanadate reagent (5 ml) was added and the content were heated on a steam bath for 10 min. Reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the absorbance was measured at 680 nm or using red filter using reagent blank and the ascorbic acid content calculated.

Results and Discussion

The accuracy (established by recovery tests based on standard addition method) and the results of estimation of ascorbic acid in biological fluids are shown in Table 1 and compared with the standard method¹⁴⁻¹⁵. The characteristic green colour at 680 nm is due to complex formation

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID WITH AMMONIUM META VANADATE REAGENT

A. Pure Sample					
Concn. µg ml ⁻¹	Mean recovery µg	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation %		
40	40.32	0.06	0.15		
200	200.00	0.25	0.13		
400	400.00	0.48	0.12		
680	680.65	0.57	0.09		
800	800.00	0.65	0.08		

B. Standard Addition Method					
Formulation	Analysis % ;		Pure ascorbic acid		Percentage recovery
	Present method	Standard method	Added mg	Found mg	
Celin (250 mg)	99.1	99.0	24.0	23.9	99.5
Sorvicin (250 mg)	99.2	99.2	24.0	23.8	99.3
Redoxan (50 mg)	99.7	99.7	24.0	23.8	99.0

C. Biological Samples					
Sample	Aliquot ml	Ascorbic acid found*			
		Present Method		Standard Method	
		µg	mg/100 ml	µg	mg/100 ml
Blood	5	58	1.16	58.5	1.17
Plasma	5	112	2.24	112	2.24
Urine	2	204	10.2	205	10.25
	2	380	19.0	381	19.05
Tomato Juice	0.5	515	103.0	515	103.0
	0.5	422	84.4	421	84.2
Lemon Juice	0.5	652	130.4	650	130.0
	0.5	755	151.0	755	151.0
Orange Juice	0.5	575	115.0	574	114.8
	0.5	734	146.8	735	147.0

* Average of three concordant determinations.

between the oxidised state of ascorbic acid (dehydroascorbic acid) and tetravalent vanadium. It obeys Beer's law between 40µg-0.8mg ml⁻¹ and the molar absorptivity for 1 µg ascorbic acid is 0.155. A green colour stable for several days, with a maximum deviation of ±1% was obtained within 10 min of heating on a steam bath. In the

NOTES

absence of oxygen and in a stream of nitrogen, the stable green colour was not obtained. Oxygen did not affect either the stability of the colour or the absorption maxima. Thus only atmospheric oxygen along with the vanadate reagent is sufficient to give a stable green colour.

References

1. J. W. STEVEN, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1938, 10, 269.
2. R. R. LALLIC and V. D. CENIC, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Belg.*, 1949, 14, 111.
3. M. K. ABRAMOV and YA. K. KEDYROV, *Aptechnoe Delo.*, 1956, 5, 28 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 5366).
4. H. LEONHERDT and W. Z. MOEGER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1941, 3, 122.
5. V. HAMANN and A. HERREMANN, *Microchim. Acta*, 1961, 105.
6. J. J. SAMUL KONAAL, *Farm. Polaska*, 1953, 11, 132.
7. J. Z. TILLMANN, P. HIRAH and W. E. HIROH, *Unterauch. Debenemilt*, 1932, 63, 1.
8. E. MARTINI and A. BONSIGNOAB, *Boll. Soc. Ital. Biol. Sper.*, 1954, 388.
9. M. Z. BARAKAT, R. R. HASSAMEIN and S. A. EL. HONY, *Bull. Acad. Focorisci. Biol.*, 1972, 20, 477.
10. M. E. DEVANI, C. J. SHISHOV and N. M. PATIL, *Indian J. Pharmacol.*, 1967, 29, 98.
11. J. H. ROE and C. KUETHER, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1963, 143, 399.
12. M. KCHOWK, *Arch. Inst. Pasteur Tunin*, 1963, 40, 25.
13. A. S. HAMNANN, *J. Appl. Chem. Biotechnol.*, 1976, 26, 611.
14. L. BERNARD and O. HAWKS, *Physiol. Chem.*, 1965, 977.
15. L. J. HARRIS and S. N. RAY, *Lancet*, 1935, 228, 71.